

Reinterpreting Statin and PCSK9 Inhibitor Effects on Endothelial Membrane Cholesterol Redistribution: The Lipoprotein Supply Hypothesis

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Abstract

Statins and PCSK9 inhibitors are among the most widely prescribed lipid-lowering drugs, and their benefits in reducing cardiovascular events are well-established. However, their precise mechanism of vascular benefit remains incompletely understood. The prevailing explanation attributes these benefits to reduced circulating LDL cholesterol. However, emerging evidence suggests that vascular endothelial health depends on adequate membrane cholesterol content, which is critical for cellular repair, lipid raft integrity, and protection against mechanical and biomechanical stresses that damage vascular membranes, and thus stabilize endothelial function, and prevent atherosclerosis. Here, I propose a novel hypothesis: the primary benefit of statins and PCSK9 inhibitors may arise from enhanced LDL receptor activity, leading to increased uptake of LDL-derived cholesterol and phospholipids into endothelial cell membranes. This redistribution of cholesterol may strengthen endothelial resilience and integrity. This commentary highlights key supporting evidence from cell culture and biochemical studies, discusses discrepancies in interpretation, and suggests directions for experimental validation. I also highlight discrepancies in current experimental data, which may reflect limitations of in vitro culture systems that do not replicate the in vivo environment of cholesterol-rich plasma.

Introduction

Atherosclerosis is traditionally viewed as a lipid accumulation disorder, yet mounting evidence suggests that endothelial dysfunction is central to disease initiation. Statins and PCSK9 inhibitors lower circulating LDL cholesterol and consistently reduce cardiovascular risk, but whether their vascular benefits are mediated solely through lipid lowering remains debated. I hypothesize that their primary benefit arises from redistribution of cholesterol into endothelial membranes via LDL receptor-mediated uptake.

Most in vitro studies of statins on endothelial cells (ECs) report reductions in plasma membrane cholesterol, lipid raft integrity, and downstream signaling.¹ However, these studies typically employ lipoprotein-depleted media, which fails to reflect the in vivo context where ECs are continuously exposed to circulating LDL and HDL particles. I propose that under physiological conditions, statins and PCSK9 inhibitors upregulate LDL receptors, thereby enhancing cholesterol uptake from plasma lipoproteins and restoring or even increasing membrane cholesterol levels. This commentary critiques existing EC culture data, highlights methodological gaps, and proposes the “lipoprotein supply hypothesis,” suggesting that vascular benefit arises from improved cholesterol availability for membrane repair, not depletion.

Hypothesis

I hypothesize that the primary mechanism by which statins and PCSK9 inhibitors reduce cardiovascular risk is through increased delivery of cholesterol and phospholipids into endothelial cell membranes. This occurs because both drug classes enhance LDL receptor

(LDLR) expression and activity, thereby promoting LDL uptake. Once internalized, LDL-derived lipids can be trafficked to the plasma membrane, restoring cholesterol content and reinforcing the endothelial barrier.² Such enrichment may improve membrane integrity, restore lipid raft-associated signaling domains, and support repair processes in response to hemodynamic shear stress and biochemical injury. This model reconciles the observed benefits of LDL lowering therapies with their endothelial protective effects.

Supporting Evidence

Several lines of evidence support this hypothesis:

1. Cell culture studies:¹ In the 2009 study "Inhibition of cholesterol biosynthesis disrupts lipid raft, caveolae and affects insulin receptor activation in 3T3-L1 preadipocytes" published in *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta* showed that inhibiting cholesterol synthesis in 3T3-L1 preadipocytes destabilizes lipid rafts and caveolae, which in turn impairs insulin receptor activation. The researchers used compounds that inhibited different stages of Mevalonate pathway of cholesterol synthesis which resulted in decreased raft and non-raft fractions of cholesterol in the adipocyte membrane. This in turn resulted in a decrease in insulin-stimulated glucose transport, indicating that cholesterol's presence in lipid rafts is crucial for proper insulin signaling. However, supplementation with exogenous cholesterol restored and even increased membrane cholesterol content. This demonstrates that external cholesterol supply can overcome statin-induced synthesis block. This mirrors the *in vivo* scenario, in which vascular endothelial cells are directly exposed to cholesterol-rich plasma. Therefore, the

discrepancy between in vitro findings and in vivo benefits of statins and PCSK9 inhibitors may be explained by differences in cholesterol availability, and the main vascular and then the clinical benefits of statins and PCSK9 inhibitors can be attributed to the net increase in LDLR activity in the vascular cell membrane.

2. Familial Hypercholesterolemia:³ Defective or absence of LDLR results in decreased or complete inability to uptake cholesterol from plasma leading to inability to repair or maintain integrity of EC membranes damaged by continuous exposure to mechanical stress of pulsatile blood pressure and biochemical stress of various injurious chemicals like advanced glycation end products (AGEs) and oxygen free radicals, thereby resulting in inflammation and early atherosclerotic events.

3. Biochemical studies:⁵ Statins upregulate LDLR expression in hepatocytes and endothelial cells, enhancing cholesterol uptake.

4. PCSK9 inhibition:⁶ By preventing LDLR degradation, PCSK9 inhibitors sustain receptor density and amplify LDL uptake in vascular endothelium.

5. Mechanistic plausibility: Vascular endothelial cells are directly exposed to LDL in plasma, making them ideal to benefit from enhanced lipid uptake.

6. In vivo vascular context:⁷ ECs express LDLR, Scavenger Receptor class B type 1 (SR-B1), and other transporters that allow continuous cholesterol exchange with plasma lipoproteins.

7. Clinical paradox: ⁸ Statins improve endothelial function (e.g., flow-mediated dilation) within weeks, even before structural plaque regression, consistent with a membrane-based functional effect.

Discussion

Current in vitro studies of statins on endothelial cells often report reduced cholesterol content, leading to interpretations that statins may disrupt lipid rafts⁴, caveolae and destabilize membranes. These findings cannot be beneficial to vascular membranes in vivo. However, these studies are typically performed in culture media lacking physiological LDL concentrations. In vivo, endothelial cells are bathed in LDL-rich plasma. Thus, when LDL uptake is upregulated by statins or PCSK9 inhibitors, net membrane cholesterol may in fact increase rather than decrease. This discrepancy underscores the need for experiments that mimic physiological lipid exposure. This hypothesis challenges the conventional view that the sole mechanism of benefit from LDL lowering therapies is reduction of circulating cholesterol. Instead, it emphasizes a dual role: lowering plasma LDL while simultaneously redistributing cholesterol into endothelial membranes. Such a framework could explain the consistent vascular protection observed with statins and PCSK9 inhibitors.

Conclusion

I propose that the key vascular benefit of statins and PCSK9 inhibitors is enhanced cholesterol and phospholipid delivery to the endothelial membrane via LDLR-mediated uptake. This ensures structural repair and stabilization of the endothelium against

hemodynamic and biochemical insults, and preservation of lipid rafts that are crucial scaffolds of various ion channels and receptors. The paradox of in vitro cholesterol depletion versus in vivo clinical improvement can be reconciled by recognizing the absence of circulating LDL in most experimental systems. Future work should employ endothelial cultures exposed to physiologic LDL concentrations, or animal models with labeled LDL tracing, to directly quantify membrane cholesterol dynamics under statin or PCSK9 inhibition. Such studies could validate whether increased LDLR-mediated uptake results in net gain of endothelial membrane cholesterol.

Table 1. In vitro vs In vivo Context of Statin Effects on Endothelial Membrane Cholesterol

Aspect	In Vitro (lipoprotein-depleted)	In Vivo (plasma with LDL/HDL)
Source of cholesterol	Endogenous synthesis only	Endogenous + continuous LDL/HDL supply
Effect of statins on synthesis	Decreased cholesterol - decreased membrane cholesterol	Decreased synthesis but increased LDLR uptake - maintained/increased cholesterol
Observed outcome	Disrupted rafts, impaired signaling	Improved endothelial function, repair

References

1. Wandelmer JS, Dávalos A, Herrera E, Giera M, Cano S, Gema de la Peña GDL, et al. Inhibition of cholesterol biosynthesis disrupts lipid raft caveolae and affects insulin receptor activation in 3T3-L1 preadipocytes. *Biochim Biophys Acta*. 2009 Sep;1788(9):1731-9. doi: 10.1016/j.bbamem.2009.05.002.

2. Ikonen E. Cellular cholesterol trafficking and compartmentalization. *Nat Rev Mol Cell Biol.* 2008;9(2):125–38. doi: 10.1038/nrm2336.
3. Brown MS, Goldstein JL. A receptor-mediated pathway for cholesterol homeostasis. *Science.* 1986;232(4746):34–47.
4. Simons K, Ikonen E. Functional rafts in cell membranes. *Nature.* 1997;387(6633):569–72. doi: 10.1038/42408.
5. Chan MLY, Shiu SWM, Cheung CL, Leung AYH, Tan KCB. Effects of statins on the inducible degrader of low-density lipoprotein receptor in familial hypercholesterolemia. *Endocr Connect.* 2022 May 13;11(6):e220019. doi: 10.1530/EC-22-0019
6. Liu C, Chen J, Chen H, Zhang T, He D, Luo Q, et al. PCSK9 Inhibition: From Current Advances to Evolving Future. *Cells.* 2022 Sep 23;11(19):2972. doi: 10.3390/cells11192972
7. Zhang X, Sessa WC, Hernando CF. Endothelial Transcytosis of Lipoproteins in Atherosclerosis. *Front Cardiovasc Med.* 2018 Sep 25;5:130. doi:10.3389/fcvm.2018.00130
8. Strey CH, Young JM, Lainchbury JH, Frampton CM, Nicholls MG, Richards AM, et al. Short - term statin treatment improves endothelial function and neurohormonal imbalance in normocholesterolaemic patients with non - ischaemic heart failure. *Heart.* 2006 May 18;92(11):1603–1609. doi: 10.1136/hrt.2005.082560